

A CASE STUDY ON WELLNESS AND SATISFACTION OF PARAMEDICAL STAFF

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Introduction

In the dynamic and high pressure environment of health care, the wellbeing and productivity of hospital employees are critical not only for the success of the organization but also for safety and satisfaction of the patients. Happiness is “an emotional or affective state that is characterized by feelings of enjoyment and satisfaction, which is often equated with morale, contentment, well-being, life satisfaction, successful aging, quality of life, and the good life.” Employee wellbeing is interlinked with physical, mental, emotional and economical fulfillment. The state of being satisfied with the job and its environment both internal and external is considered to be a constituent of employee well-being and happiness. The hospital employees and their satisfaction have direct impact with the customers services. The hospital employees are the important stake holder of the business. The happy employee will ensure quality service to the patients and make them happy and unhappy employee make some mistakes or near miss or an error which may end up in unpredictable loss to the patients and organization. The patients and attenders were very sensitive towards the kind of service given by the hospital staff. The hospital is the residential establishment providing preventive, diagnostic, curative, and rehabilitative services through the inpatient and outpatient departments. The hospital functions only with the hands of its employees.

The study was conducted at a multispecialty hospital in the Madurai district of Tamil Nadu, India. It covers the paramedical staff working in the hospital. The researcher collected the information from the data sheets, which consist of 25 variables related to employee well-being. The employees rated the variables with a 1 to 5 Likert rating scale from ‘highly unsatisfied’ to ‘highly satisfied’. 100 samples were taken for the study.

Key words: Employee wellness, Health care workers, Hospital employee satisfaction.

Statement of the problem

Hospitals depend on a diverse workforce-doctors, nurses, technicians, and administrative staff, each playing a vital role in delivering quality care. Understanding what drives employee happiness and efficiency is essential for creating a sustainable and high-performing workplace. So, this is considered the pivotal factor for the business. Health care employee happiness and wellbeing will increase job satisfaction, reduce employee turnover and attrition, and improve the quality of healthcare services.

Objective of the study

The study was conducted at a multi-specialty tertiary care centre among the paramedical staff members to understand their satisfaction related to their job and internal environment, work activity, work relationship, and utilization and development of their skill and potential.

Hypothesis testing

1. **Null Hypothesis (H_0):** The true mean = 0 (no satisfaction).
2. **Alternative Hypothesis (H_1):** The true mean \neq 0 (significant satisfaction/dissatisfaction).

Scope of the study

The study has been conducted in a NABH accredited multi-specialty Hospital to analyse the factors affecting the employee wellbeing. The study conducted through survey form with the help of human resource executive and quality executive among the paramedical staff working in the various department of the hospital. The results of this study can be limited only to the same type of hospital setting.

Review of literature

Employee wellbeing refers to a professional's holistic state of mental, emotional and physical health. According to Gallup researchers, employee wellbeing includes five core components: Career wellbeing. The satisfaction people feel with work responsibilities and how they spend their time at work every day. It is been state that Pillars of employee wellbeing- healthy relationship, career satisfaction, financial security, physical health and community connections. The study on importance of work environment performance (Yoon H. J., Kim S.Y., 2013) examines how high-performance work environments (HPWEs) in hospitals contribute to better employee retention, increased job satisfaction, and improved patient care outcomes. It highlights the significance of supportive management practices and employee engagement in fostering a positive workplace culture. The scoping review (Korhonen, A., Kallioma-Puha, L., & Salminen, H. (2024)) focuses on factors affecting nurses' well-being in hospital environments, identifying key elements such as managerial support, work-life balance, and organizational culture that influence job satisfaction and performance. The systematic review (Meyers, M. C., van Woerkom, M., & Bakker, A. B. (2023)) evaluates the effectiveness of positive psychology interventions (PPIs) in enhancing the well-being of healthcare workers, finding that PPIs can reduce symptoms of depression, anxiety, and burnout while increasing job satisfaction and resilience. This article (Taguchi, A., Takahashi, M., & Hiraoka, K. (2024)) investigates the association between health and productivity management practices in hospitals and the work engagement levels of nurses, emphasizing the role of supportive workplace policies in promoting employee well-being and organizational performance. This study (Pagnucci, N., Arcangeli, G., & Giusino, D. (2023)). explores the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on workplace well-being and productivity, discussing strategies such as mindfulness and stress management techniques to enhance employee resilience and performance during challenging times In 2014, a study of the European Agency for Safety and Health at Work underlined that perceived job insecurity, task organization, and number of working hours were responsible for a decrease in happiness at the workplace.

Good leadership can empower employees to work better towards reaching the organisation's goals. Theories of well-being are often classified into hedonistic theories, desire theories, and objective list theories. According to Hedonistic theories and desire theories are subjective theories, the degree of well-being of a person depends on the subjective mental states and attitudes of this person. Objective list theories, on the other hand, allow that things can benefit a person independent of that person's subjective attitudes. Objective list theories state that a person's well-being depends on a variety of basic objective goods. These goods may also include subjective factors like a pleasure-pain-balance or desire-satisfaction besides factors that are independent of the subject's attitudes, like friendship or having virtues. The job position, working style, and working units significantly affects the employee happiness and their quality of life. Autonomy in carrying out job duties and other job-related tasks

significantly contributed to employee happiness. According to one study Clergy, CEO's, Agriculturist, Company Secretaries, Regulatory professional, Health managers, Medical Professionals, Farmers and Accommodation managers are the happiest jobs in that order in another study. On the other hand, social workers, nurses, social workers, medical doctors, and psychiatrists abuse substances and incur mental ill-health at among the highest rates of any occupation. For instance, the psychiatrist burnout rate is 40%.

Albert Schweitzer once stated that “success is not the key to happiness, happiness is the key to success.” Despite this widespread belief, employee happiness is often perceived by organizations as an insubstantial topic, irrelevant to bottom-line outcomes. Equally as problematic, past investigations have primarily utilized other positive emotion variables as a proxy for happiness, thus convoluting the relationships between happiness and work outcomes. Happiness in the workplace is usually dependent on the work environment. During the past two decades, maintaining a level of happiness at work has become more significant and relevant due to the intensification of work caused by economic uncertainty and increase in competition. It is thus beneficial for companies to create and maintain positive work environments and leadership that will contribute to the happiness of their employees. Happiness is not fundamentally rooted in obtaining sensual pleasures and money, but those factors can influence the well-being of an individual at the workplace. The study by Mousavi (2019) at Iran assesses the happiness and professional autonomy states that the nurses are moderately happy with the freedom in their work. The systematic review was conducted by Arulappan (2021) from August 2010 to August 2020 using Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses on the predictors of nurses happiness. Job-related predictors were identified as organizational predictors; and personal, psychological, family, social, and spiritual predictors were reported to be the individual predictors. As both individual and organizational predictors determine the happiness of nurses A study by Bellet, (2024) proves that one unit increase in happiness, on a standard 0-to-10 scale, leads to around 3 additional weekly sales, around a 12% increase in the productivity. Three potential productivity channels behind the effect of happiness on sales performance are time management with work schedule, work faster and increasing the sales. Thompson (2021) noted evidence for employee happiness’s ability to significantly mediate the relationship between job demands and organizational outcomes. The University of Warwick, UK, mentioned in one of their studies that happy workers are up to 12% more productive than unhappy professionals. Employee happiness is one of the interesting and hot topics (Fisher, 2010). Researchers and practitioners have already started exploring this topic with other different aspects. No doubt, studies are available on employee happiness or workplace happiness with other variables (Bajaj & Krishnan, 2016) looks at procedural, distributive, and interactional justice as antecedents of perceived organizational support and leader-member exchange. It also looks at the effect of all these on positive and negative affect the happiness of employee at work. As per (Wok, S., & Hashim, J 2015) the female workers happy to work with the organisation with mutual rewards to one another, which depicts the social exchange theory. Organizational culture represents the internal work environment created for operating an organisation. It can also represent how employees are treated by their bosses and peers. An effective organisation should have a culture that takes into account employee's happiness and encourages employee satisfaction. The income-happiness relationship suggested that income and happiness at work are positively correlated, and the relationship is stronger for individuals with extrinsic value orientations. Job security is an important factor to determine whether employees feel happiness at work. Career development, the chances of higher promotion motivate the employee and makes happy. Job autonomy may be defined as the condition of being self-governing or free from excessive external control in the workplace

environment. The German philosopher Immanuel Kant believed that autonomy is important to human beings because it is the foundation of human dignity and the source of all morality.

Research Methodology

This is a qualitative and descriptive study, observed the phenomenon of the happenings and the researcher does not have any control over the variable. Both primary and secondary data were used for the study. Primary data collected from the respondents of the research area and the secondary data collected from the documents, books and the journals. The data analyzed with descriptive statistics using SPSS.

The study was conducted at a multispecialty hospital in Madurai district. The hospital is a NABH accredited 200 bedded private hospital serves the with 31 specialties and also accredited with National Board of Medical Sciences in specialties for providing training to Post graduates residents in the areas of Family Medicine, Paediatrics, Emergency Medicine, Radio diagnosis and anesthesiology.

The study conducted between February 2024 to March 2024. The standard questionnaire used for data collection from the hospital staff and 5-point Likert scale from ‘1’ as highly unsatisfied to ‘5’ as highly satisfied. The variables related to happiness such as physical environment, working hours, supervision and guidance, leave management, remuneration, opportunities for promotion, employee benefits, job security, authority and independence, and relationship with coworkers have been taken for the study.

Data Analysis and interpretations

Percentage analysis has been applied for all variables using SPSS 20 version. The tables and percentage analysis were employed to study the results. One sample T test, Tables and barchart used to analyse the data.

Hospital employee profile

GENDER		Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	81	81.0	81.0
	Male	19	19.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	

Table - Gender

Majority of the hospital employees, 81 percent were female and 19 percent were male. 41 percent of the staff belong to the 31- to 40-year-old age group, 40 percent of the staff belong to the 20- to 30-year-old age group, 14 percent of the staff belong to the 41- to 50-year-old age group, and 5 percent belong to the 50-year-old and above age group.

Age		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20-30	40	40.0	40.0
	31-40	41	41.0	81.0
	41-50	14	14.0	95.0
	50 and above	5	5.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	

Table - Age Group

With regard to the department 21 percentage of the respondents were working with administration and 11 percentage of the respondents were working with housekeeping, 9 percentage of the respondents were working with front office, 36 percentage of the respondents were working with nursing, 8 percentage of the respondents were working with laboratory and 11 percentage of the respondents were working with pharmacy. With regard to the job position 21 percentage of the respondents were assistants 35 percentage of the respondents were nursing staff, 10 percentage of the respondents were working as executive, 11 percentage of the respondents were working as technicians and 11 percentage as cleaner, 3 percentage of the respondents were pharmacist, 9 percentage of the respondents were patient relation officer.

Designation		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Assistant	21	21.0	21.0
	Nursing Staff	35	35.0	56.0
	Executive	10	10.0	66.0
	Technician	11	11.0	77.0
	Cleaner	11	11.0	88.0
	Pharmacist	3	3.0	91.0
	Patient relation officer	9	9.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	

Table - Job designation

Factors impacting the paramedical staff's well-being at the workplace

Work environment of the paramedical staff concerning the physical environment of the working place, 15% were not satisfied and 55% were satisfied, and 30% were highly satisfied. Related to the working hours of the paramedical staff, 33 percent were unsatisfied, and 67 percent were satisfied. The pay remuneration received by the paramedical staff is satisfactory for 58 percent and unsatisfactory for 42 percent of them. The job security at the organization satisfies 64 percent of the paramedical staff, 36 percent were unsatisfied. The supervision and guidance provided by the hospital management was satisfactory for 84 percent unsatisfactory for 16 percent of the staff. Concerning the authority and independence enjoyed at their work was satisfactory for 76 percent and unsatisfactory for 24 percent of the staff. About promotion opportunities, 62 percent were satisfied, and 38 percent of the staff were unsatisfied. Related to the employee benefits, 67 percent were satisfied, and 33 percent of the employees were unsatisfied. Regarding the relationship with coworkers, 88 percent of the paramedical staff were satisfied, and 12 percent were unsatisfied.

One sample t test

One-Sample Test						
	Test Value = 0					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
physical environment	56.036	99	.000	4.100	3.95	4.25
Working hours per week	25.557	99	.000	3.220	2.97	3.47
Supervision and guidance to perform Work	25.806	99	.000	3.110	2.87	3.35
Leave Management	36.443	99	.000	3.730	3.53	3.93
Remuneration	26.566	99	.000	3.370	3.12	3.62
Increments and appraisals	21.963	99	.000	2.640	2.40	2.88
Opportunities for Promotion	27.458	99	.000	3.300	3.06	3.54
Benefits (Health Insurance,life insurance etc	27.997	99	.000	3.480	3.23	3.73
Job Security	29.627	99	.000	3.780	3.53	4.03
Recognition For work Accomplished	29.972	98	.000	3.333	3.11	3.55
Job Responsibilities	26.416	99	.000	3.400	3.14	3.66
Authority & Independence given to Accomplish Task	34.202	99	.000	3.650	3.44	3.86
Relationships with your co-workers	29.267	99	.000	3.540	3.30	3.78
Relationships with your Supervisor	29.839	99	.000	3.510	3.28	3.74
Relationships with your Subordinates(if Applicable)	31.979	94	.000	3.684	3.46	3.91

One-Sample t-Test compares each factor's average score against a hypothetical population mean of 0, testing if the factor is significantly higher than zero (a test of positive perception). All p-values (Sig. (2-tailed)) are 0.000, which is < 0.05, so we reject the null hypothesis in all cases. This confirms that employees report statistically significant levels of satisfaction in every factor. The factors such as physical environment (mean 4.10) highly rated work conditions, working hours (mean 3.22) moderately acceptable by the staff, Supervision (mean 3.11) needs improvement, Leave Management (mean 3.73) satisfactory for the staff, Remuneration (mean - 3.37) found average, Appraisals (mean 2.64) below average (needs attention), Promotion Opportunities (mean 3.30) average, Benefits (Health, Life Insurance, etc.) (Mean 3.48) found Satisfactory.

Job Security (mean 3.78) shows strong sense of security, Recognition of work (mean 3.33) shows moderate satisfaction, Job Responsibilities (mean 3.40) well balanced. Authority & Independence (mean 3.65) indicates high autonomy, Co-worker Relationships (mean 3.54) ensure positive interpersonal climate, and Supervisor Relationships (mean 3.5) found strong, Subordinate Relationships (mean 3.68) reveals outstanding team dynamics among the work group.

Discussion

According to Puteri, L. A., & Syaebani, M. I. (2018) the people who work in the medical division have a higher level of stress compared to other divisions. The study highlighted that nursing staff comprised the largest segment of paramedical 35% of the total respondents, followed by administrative staff at 21%. The high level of satisfaction with the physical environment indicates that the facilities and workspace conditions are generally well-regarded among staff members. A majority of (82%) of respondents expressed satisfaction, with their work schedules. These findings suggest that time management and shift allocation practices are largely effective and appreciated by the staff. Similarly, supervision and guidance received favorable feedback. 46% of the respondents stated they were satisfied, and 38% were highly satisfied with the support and oversight they received in their roles denotes that there is an existing constructive and supportive supervisory system in place in the organization. Overall, the data underscores a generally positive work environment among paramedical staff, with notable strengths in physical infrastructure, working hours, and supervisory support. Paramedics were satisfied with leave management, in terms of remuneration, 58% were satisfied. When asked about opportunities for promotion 70% expressed satisfaction, regarding employee benefits, 67% were satisfied. 43% were satisfied with employee benefits, and 31% were neutral regarding job security. In the area of authority and independence, 76% of respondents were satisfied, Lastly, 83% of respondents were satisfied with their relationship with co-workers.

Conclusion

The study was conducted in a NABH-accredited hospital. The study concluded that factors such as Physical Environment, Job Security, Independence, Subordinate & Supervisor relationships were highly rated. Some factors like Increments & Appraisals (2.64) is the most critical weakness. Supervision (3.11) & Working Hours (3.22) require review and enhancement as they were low rated or not up to the satisfaction of the paramedical staff, which may need improvements. This denoted that there is need to improve appraisal systems fairness, transparency, and recognition. The management has to review work volume of the staff and type of supervision and guidance provided in performing the work thereby they receive clearer guidance and better manager training. It is essential to maintain and continue investing with physical environment and insurance benefits to maintain employee morale. The management should focus on strengthen career growth paths especially for departments with low promotion scores.

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